

Qualitative Study on Effective Pedagogy for Sustainable Primary Level of Education in Nigeria: Review on Post Covid-19 Era

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Abstract

This paper is qualitative in nature which analysed the impact of an infectious disease known as CORONA VIRUS (COVID-19) on primary education activities in Nigeria, and discussed on the importance of employing proper pedagogy as a measure to argument the challenges posed as a result of the corona virus. Secondary data was used in this research as a source of information to discuss the topic. The paper therefore discussed on the emergence of COVID-19, its impact on education activities, as well as pedagogical measures to be taken in case of encountering such calamities to maintain sustainable education. The research finds out among others that education activities were halted, as schools were closed for a long period of time as part of control measure to curve the spread and prevent carriage to other vulnerable individuals. The paper concluded that measures taken have thwarted education sector which called for change from face-to-face education delivery to the use of technological pedagogy. It recommended among others that e-learning materials should be made available to take care of such scenarios in future.

Keywords: Primary Education; Pedagogy; Post-Covid

Introduction

Education is of no doubt a tool for change. Change which affects the entire human lives; being it morally; physically; mentally; emotionally and spiritually. There is a believed that to deprive a nation from progress is as simple as to deny that nation education to its citizens. Thus, lack of education has diverse and far reaching consequences on the entire life of an individual and community in general (Allison Academy, 2021).

Education is classified as one of the fundamental human rights, but, many countries are unable to provide it to its citizens due to one reason or another, especially a qualitative education for that matter. Accordingly, UNESCO Institute of Statistics (UIS), 2018 reported in its annual data in 2018 that 59 million children of primary school age were out of school. Nigeria as one of the signatories to the United Nations' Human Right Charter is bound to Article 26, sub-sections (1) and (2) which clearly stated that every individual is entitle to, at the basic stage, free and compulsory education, and should be available and equally accessible to all, which would be directed to the full development of human personality and strengthen of respect for human rights and fundamental freedom, promote understanding, tolerance and friendliness among all (Onyebu & Okanume-Ohan, 2014).

Dolezalova in Janis (2014) opined that education has accompanied humanity throughout its historical evolution since the ancient times and is part of everyone's entire life. Education is a versatile phenomenon, depending on the changes of people's conditions of life. When human intellectual abilities reached a certain degree during the initial stage of human development, the behaviour of people ceased to be governed just by instincts, and deliberate conduct and actions became more important. It was at this moment when people broke free from the animal kingdom; this is proven by education, meaning the care for offspring, as a targeted and anticipative activity.

For many years since the beginning of the history of education, the principles of how children should be brought up were passed from parents onto their children. Scholars were contemplating about education, its targets and ideals, but the ideas were not tested in practice. In the middle Ages, education was strongly influenced by religious philosophy, by Christianity. Enlightenment brought new ideas about humans and the creation of the first theoretical systems focusing on educational systems. The thinking, however, still predominantly dealt with specific procedures. By the 19th century, sufficient know-how about education was collected, allowing scholars to draw generalizations, use scientific terminology and form an independent discipline. The scientific discipline focusing on education and humans in educational situations was called pedagogy (Dolezalova in Janis, 2014)

Each individual has his/her idea about education, upbringing and instruction, based primarily on the experience with education within family and at school. Pedagogy as a science is different, as it describes the phenomenon on the basis of scientific findings. It is based on the results of the verification of theories, hypotheses and empirical findings.

Deterioration of facilities, inadequate funding, unqualified teaching personnel, lack of teaching aids, obsolete libraries/laboratory equipments and poor and polluted learning environment are among other factors responsible for decline in standard of education. While, the primary level of education as considered the foundational level needs to be funded, controlled and managed very well, as providing adequate education to citizens impacted socioeconomics growth and development (Samphina Academy, 2017).

UNESCO as a single United Nations agency mandated to cover all aspects of education across the globe opined that education transforms lives; thus, the mission of the Organisation is to “build peace, eradicate poverty and drive sustainable development” (UNESCO, 2023).

Suddenly, in March 2020 education activities were abruptly disrupted due to the declaration of COVID 19 as a global pandemic. Thus, schools and all other educational activities were stopped in order to curb further spread of COVID-19 pandemic in almost all countries.

Nowadays, education is much concern with personalization, participation and production as per instruction delivery is concerned. In other words, teaching/learning delivery involves learning through authentic real world contexts, conducting comprehensive project activities as well as solving immediate problems (Ali, Mondal & Das, 2018).

In precise, one can conclude that people cannot do without education, which is why they apply it in their lives. Education has been part of the entire human history and one’s entire life. Its targeted and well-considered nature which focuses on the development of individuals differentiates education from other activities and impacts. Education is primarily vital and indispensable in childhood. It focuses on shaping the relationships toward all important conditions in life – toward oneself, other people and the nature around. Objectives, content and means of education change throughout the development of mankind.

Emergence of Corona Virus (COVID-19) in Nigeria

Tang, (2022) reported that corona virus disease 2019, well known as COVID-19, caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), was first reported in Wuhan China on December 8, 2019. Since then, it has spread quickly to different parts of the world. He further narrated that as of July 15, 2021, 08:11 GMT, 189,190,520 people were infected by COVID-19 globally and 4,074,788 deaths were reported (Our World in Data, 2021 in Tang, 2022). Lockdown has been initiated at the onset of COVID-19 and has been adaptively implemented in different countries depending on the number of COVID-19 cases. United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF), 2023 reported that on March 11, 2020, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a global pandemic, resulting in disruptions to education at an unprecedented scale.

Ibrahim and Uba (2022) reported that on 27 February 2020, in Lagos State, the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health echoed the first verified case of COVID-19. The multi-sector corona virus preparedness team, led by the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control [NCDC], has immediately activated its National Emergency Operations Centre [NEOC]. Ibrahim and Uba (2022) further corroborated that the Federal Government of Nigeria issued a number of directives combat sanctions and structural changes across the country to curtail further spread of COVID-19. These directives range from the closure of international airports to the closure of all schools across the country and the lockdown declared in several key states – Lagos, Abuja, Kano and Ogun - for several weeks at the beginning.

In comply to the directives given by the Federal Government, Ejeh et al., (2020); Obiakor, Adeniran, (2020) in Ibrahim and Uba, (2022) stated that the Federal Ministry of Education issued a circular on 19 March 2020, authorizing the closure of all schools for one month from Monday 23 March 2020, to prevent the spread of COVID-19, which affects nearly 46 million students and children across the country, thus, academic activities cannot continue because of the lockdown, as, the COVID-19 epidemic had led to a partial or complete “lockdown” in many countries.

Impact of COVID-19 on Primary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Fana et al., (2020); Tang, (2021a) in Tang, (2022) stated that the spread of COVID-19 has multiple impacts on the socioeconomic systems. Lock-down has resulted in the temporary and selective closure of businesses and services which prompts employers to adopt different employment patterns, for instance, by partially or entirely shifting from full-time employment to part-time and casual employment in relation to operational demands during various stages of COVID-19 lockdown.

Fana et al., (2020) in Tang (2022) maintained that the uncertainties brought by COVID-19 lockdown on businesses has an impact on the workforce, causing a significant reduction in the demand for work- force in sectors most affected by the lockdown, particularly education, hospital and aviation. In addition, self-isolation and travel restriction as a result of COVID-19 lockdown have catalyzed the deployment of online operational mode in many sectors such as education, retails, food and beverages as well as banking (Fairlie & Fossen, 2021; & Tang, 2020a in Tang, 2022).

The education sector has been hard-hit by COVID-19 since the very beginning. While different countries have different policies on the operation of education centers, many education centers have been closed since the onset of COVID-19 (Tang, 2021b in Tang, 2022).

In Nigeria during the shutdown, Dreesen et al., (2020) and UNESCO, (2020) in Ibrahim and Uba, (2022) indicated that learning and access to essential school services had been disrupted, as a record number of students and pupils were prevented from school due to lockdowns, which affected approximately 46 million students and pupils nationwide, including more than 91 % of primary and secondary school students.

The impacts of school closures were wide-ranging, affecting not only children's schooling and learning, but also their health and nutrition, mental wellbeing, and protection against child labour, gender-based violence and more. As a result, Ifijeh & Yusuf, (2020); Ho et al., (2021); and Zawacki-Richter, (2021) in Ibrahim and Uba (2022) have shown the importance of using electronic media in distance learning programmes. Though, they indicated that the use of electronic media in distance education programmes is not only focused on digital technologies, but also includes physical administration.

Ibrahim and Uba (2022) reported that as a result of the outbreak, Nigerian education was disrupted; students' access to schools across the country was restricted. Therefore, the epidemic COVID-19 poses significant problems for the stakeholders: government; students and parents as it exposes and potentially exacerbates existing deficiencies in the education system (Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020 in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022). Thus, a crucial question arises as the country grapples with these problems, as is the Nigerian education system designed to adapt quickly to changing circumstances? Given the current global circumstances, the country's ability to ensure continuous learning will depend primarily on its ability to quickly harness existing technologies, create appropriate infrastructure and mobilize partners to develop alternative education programmes (Owolabi et al., 2013, in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022).

The COVID-19 pandemic had affected the education system, particularly basic education, and especially for pupils, students and parents of public schools. Subsequently, pupils, trainees and students can use effective resources such as information and communication technology (ICT) to explore things that interest them and actively learn during the lockdown and beyond.

Unfortunately, the Nigerian education system is unable to adapt to the challenges of COVID-19 and the country struggled in the area of information and communication technology especially at public primary level of education for the foreseeable future. However, compared to private schools, public school students face a disproportionate socio-economic burden. While several private schools have started distance education programmes and are taking advantage of the many Media Education (Mediaobrazovanie, 2022 in Ibrahim & Uba, 2022)

Effective Pedagogy for Sustainable Primary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Kapur (2020) opined that pedagogy is concerned with the teaching processes. Westbrook et al. (2013) observed that pedagogy itself is a contested term, but involves activities that evoke changes in the learner: Watkins and Mortimore (1999, p.3) in Westbrook et al. (2013) define pedagogy as 'any conscious activity by one person designed to enhance learning in another'. According to Bernstein (2000, p.78) also in Westbrook et al. (2013), pedagogy 'is a sustained process whereby somebody(s) acquires new forms or develops existing forms of conduct, knowledge, practice and criteria from somebody(s) or something deemed to be an appropriate provider and evaluator'.

It is the study of how knowledge and competencies are imparted in the educational framework. Learning cannot take place in seclusion, it is indispensable for the individuals to interact with each other and form cordial terms and relationships. By the 19th century, sufficient know-how about education was collected, allowing scholars to draw generalizations, use scientific terminology and form an independent discipline. The scientific discipline focusing on education and humans in educational situations was called pedagogy. (Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014).

Pedagogy is an encompassing term concerned with what a teacher does to influence learning in others. As the importance of high quality education for children has become more clearly understood, so has the teacher/educator's role in the provision of these services. This demands a clear understanding of the meaning of pedagogy and how it plays out in individual educators and services (Ali, Mondal & Das, 2018).

According to Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014, pedagogy is an independent social anthroposophic science (science about humans) that represents an organized system of findings about educational processes and its results, conditions and factors which determine the education, as well as the main agents of the process. Pedagogy studies education in its versatility and diversity, and it describes, explains, compares, evaluates and generalizes the findings about pedagogical phenomena. It reveals and formulates the pedagogical principles and rules which reflect the relationships and connections in educational practice.

Based on these facts, pedagogy proposes constructs and concepts (theories, models, plans) which are subsequently verified in practice. The findings are thus specified and a pedagogical theory is developed, together with other fields within interdisciplinary character. In other words, pedagogy is a normative science (formulating norms, rules, principles and guidelines for education and upbringing) and a descriptive science. It is also an explorative science (exploring and studying new educational phenomena), as well as an explanatory science (identifying and explaining processes, results and factors of education), which is an essential activity for pedagogy. And last but not least, it is a projecting science (proposing new and more effective processes, resources or entire programmes). Sometimes, the aforementioned attributes are all described as functions of pedagogy (Dolezalova, Habl & Janis, 2014).

Kapur (2020) believed that in education affairs instructors regard pedagogy as an essential part of the teaching-learning methods and instructional strategies, therefore, having a well-thought out pedagogy can bring about improvements in the quality of life of teaching/learning process. He further argued that when students are admitted in schools, certain concepts will be new to them, thus, they will need help in understanding these concepts, and guide to adopt to the new environment. Being aware in terms of the methods one can teach and facilitate student learning can contribute effectively in acquiring an understanding in terms of importance of pedagogy.

Pedagogy is regarded as an academic discipline, henceforth, educators need to clearly understand the needs and requirements of the students, students on the other hand too need to obey their instructors and follow the rules and instructions. Consequently, when these factors are put into practice in an effectual manner, the importance of pedagogy is recognized.

Pedagogy is the act of teaching, where at the beginning instructors made use of traditional methods in imparting knowledge and understanding to the students in terms of lesson plans and academic concepts. But with the advent of technologies, teachers are making use of technologies and other modern and innovative methods in facilitating learning. Apart from utilization of technologies, the instructors are making use of modern, scientific and innovative methods in facilitating learning. The examples of these methods are charts, graphs, images, pictures, diagrams, articles, models, and so forth.

Entz, 2006 in Kapur (2020) suggested that there are various factors that are needed to be taken into consideration in the implementation of proper pedagogical methods in an efficacious manner. These are, needs and requirements of the students, their age groups and grade levels, academic subjects and lesson plans and overall system of education. The students should take pleasure and develop motivation among themselves in facilitating learning. Therefore, it is well-understood, when the utilization of these methods prove to be advantageous and meaningful to the students and facilitate the achievement of academic goals, the individuals are able to understand the importance of pedagogy.

When the pedagogical methods are put into operation in teaching and learning processes, they are not merely referred to imparting knowledge and understanding to the students in terms of lesson plans and academic concepts, but they take into account other factors as well. One of the important factors that is taken into account is, Student-Centred Teaching and Learning (SCL) approach. This approach is reflective in their theory, practice, policy implementation in the teaching and learning processes, and results in positive impacts in terms of the learners. The meaning of this approach is, the teaching and the learning methods that are put into practice should have the main aim of facilitating student learning and up-grading the overall system of education. The teaching and learning are regarded as complicated processes, and these are indispensable ways of promoting student learning and leading to effective growth and development of the system of education (Entz, 2006 in Kapur, 2020). Therefore, it is comprehensively understood that the importance of pedagogy is recognized, when it plays an important part in facilitating student learning and enriching the overall system of education.

Primary School Level of Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

Education is the conscious transmission of the knowledge, values and skills acquired by society from one generation to the next through institutions. Consequently, an adequate education system is necessary for the advancement of individuals in society and the economy. The impact of repeated lockdown of schools and academic programmes on student learning can have detrimental consequences for students, parents and the nation. (Ibrahim & Uba, 2022).

Otamiri (2022) described education as to what can be used by man to solve his problems to improve his life and make it comfortable. He further said it is one of the several ways that man employs to bring change into his all-round development. Education demands efforts and discipline. It is also a formidable tool for man's survival. Ayu (1991) conceived education as what brings about the moral development and spiritual upliftment of the human personality and of the community as a whole. He stressed further that education makes mankind more creative and enables him to live a more fulfilling life through interaction.

Development on the other hand as described by Pettinger, (2018) in Otamiri (2022) is concerned with how people in a country or economic system are actually affected. It looks at their actual living standards and the freedom they have to

enjoy a good standard of living (Pettinger, 2018 in Otamiri, 2022). Otamiri (2021) further stated that to define national development, there should be focus on the extent to which the institutions of a given society enhance the capacity of the people, as individuals and as a social collective, to ensure the conditions for the persistence of social life. Thus, a developed economy is one that has the basic structure, infrastructure and values that guarantee human life and the full attainment of human aspirations. This implies that, for there to be development in the nation, there should be a concerted effort to establish institutional frameworks that would guarantee individual and social creativity, fulfilment, and provision of social amenities, education, health services, security, shelter, and food for human healthy existence and fulfilment. It also implies that development necessitates an establishment of social framework for institutionalization of social values for social cooperation. Thus, a society devoid of these ideal socio- economic characteristics cannot be described as a developed society; they are either developing or under-developed.

Development refers to an improvement in the quality of life and living standards, e.g. measures of literacy, life-expectancy and health care, it looks at a wider range of statistics than just GDP per capita. Economic development involves the improvement of human capital, literacy ratio, important infrastructure, health and safety, and other areas that aim at increasing the general welfare of the citizens (Chukwuka & Ananaba, 2016 in Otamiri, 2022). Development can also be seen as an increase in living conditions, improvement of the self-esteem needs and a free and just society (Todaro, 2016). He suggests that the most accurate method of measuring economic development is Human Development index which takes into account the literacy rate which in turn has outright impact on productivity and could lead to economic growth (Todaro, 2016). From the above citations, development refers to a level of societal living characterized by major changes in various aspects of human and social life such as economic, political, institutional, cultural, etc.

A developing economy on the other hand as prescribed by Otamiri (2022) is one where people have a lower standard of living and less developed industries than other countries. A developing economy is a nation where the average income is much lower than in industrial nations, where the economy relies on a few export crops, and where farming is conducted by primitive methods (Otamiri, 2021). Unfortunately, Nigeria falls within this pitiable economic reality of a developing economy. Nigeria as a country is blessed with abundance of human and natural resources (such as crude oil, tin, zinc, cocoa, groundnut, etc.) which nature has endowed on her. The country's climate conditions favour wide variety of agricultural and economic resource activities. Additionally, Nigeria is the most populous country in the continent of Africa, with abundant economic resources. Her people are still suffering in abject poverty and impoverishment, poor and ineffective infrastructural facilities, low and primitive service delivery, industrial development still below average, and still remains a developing economy.

Sustainable development can be seen as a development that meets our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (United Nations, 2009 in Otamiri & Odu, 2022). Three elements were further identified which should work together to ensure sustainable development. These include: economic development; social development and environmental protection.

Ayeni in Otamiri and Odu (2022) argues that these three components must be conceptualized together, planned together and implemented together to achieve the desired results. Development can only make sense to the people when they are involved in the process of decision making through a Bottom-top approach.

Moreover, sustainable development as conceptualized by Otamiri and Odu (2022) is the extent to which a country has developed may be assessed by considering a range of narrow and broad indicators, including per capita income, life expectancy, education, and the extent of poverty alleviation. A sustainable development is that development that is stable, enduring, and consistent. It is a development that lasts and does not crumble in the face of formidable problems. Sustainable development is a development that does not roll back or recede, even in the face of threatening reversal waves (Omotola, 2006 in Otamiri & Odu, 2022).

Conclusion

The paper discusses on the emergence of Covid-19 pandemic which brought historic education disruptions which include prolonged schools closure around the globe. It pointed out how the pandemic upset the education system particularly at primary level of education in Nigeria as one of the developing nations struggled with economic dwindling, which left her with no option than to use face-face method of teaching prior to COVID-19 pandemic. The paper also identified some challenges faced by the education sector such as inadequate plans to provide distance education, especially for public primary schools, due to lack of funds and inadequate planning. It further discusses on how utilizing proper pedagogies could aid and facilitate teaching/learning activities in case of future reoccurrence.

Recommendations

The paper recommended the following:

1. Government should provide primary schools with adequate number of instructional gadgets to cater for e-learning needs in case of reoccurrence of same scenario as corona virus period
2. Teachers should be well trained in the field of information and technology so as to be equipped and well prepared to handle any challenged posed by unforeseen situation
3. Learners should be trained on how to acquire knowledge through the use of audio materials (such as radio), audio-visual (such as television) and so on.
4. Adequate infrastructure should be provided so that distance could be observed appropriately when the need arise.
5. Adequate provisions need to be made to face such challenges through the use of technology, as well as support of appropriate education methodologies/pedagogies.

References

- Ali, R., Mondal, M. & Das, T. (2018). Pedagogy and the role of teachers in the teaching learning process. Allison Academy (2021). Lack of education: causes and effects. https://www.allisonacademy.com/students/education/higher-education_retrieved_on_2/09/2023
- Dolezalova, J., Habl, J. & Janis, K. (2014). Fundamental pedagogy. Edited by Janis, K. P.4-140
- Ibrahim, A., M. & Uba, S., (2022). COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown on education: proposing an ‘e-pedagogy on the go’ system as an alternative e-teaching and learning platform during and in the post-pandemic era. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359344328>. DOI:10.13187/me.2022.1.63
- Kapur, R. (2020). Understanding the meaning and significance of pedagogy. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345156519_Understanding_the_Meaning_and_Ssignificance_of_Pedagogy.
- Onyebu, N., G. & Okanume-Onah, A., V. (2014). Access to qualitative basic education in Nigeria: from policy to practice. *Academic Discourse: An International Journal* V 7 (1)
- Otamiri, S. & Odu, S. (2022). Education, sustainable development, covid-19 pandemic, and digital revolution model. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358304701>
- Samphina Academy (2017). Factors responsible for poor nursery/primary education in Nigeria. <https://samphina.com.ng/factors-responsible-poor-nursery-primary-education-nigeria>
- Tang, K., H., D. (2022) Impacts of COVID-19 on primary, secondary and tertiary education: a comprehensive review and recommendations for educational practices. *Educational Research for Policy and Practice*. 22:23–61 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10671-022-09319-y>
- UNESCO (2023). Education transforms lives. <https://www.unesco.org/en/education>
- UNESCO, (2018). Out-of-school children and youth. https://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/out-school-children-and-youth_retrieved_on_01/09/2023
- Westbrook, J., Durrani, N., Brown, R., Orr, D., Pryor, J., Boddy, J. & Salvi, F. (2013). Pedagogy, curriculum, teaching practices and teacher education in developing countries. Final Report. Education Rigorous Literature Review. Department for International Development.